

Analytical application of *m*-methylphenylazo-bis-acetoxime in the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II)

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m-Methylphenylazo-bis-acetoxime has been used for spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II). The complex absorbs at 394 nm and the Beer's law validity has been checked. Stability constants have been calculated. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are 2258 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 26.10 ng cm⁻², respectively.

Arylazo-bis-acetoximes are similar to hydroxytriazenes. Although a number of studies related to cobalt(II) determination using hydroxytriazenes as reagents have been done¹, no study has yet appeared on arylazo-bis-acetoximes. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken.

Results and discussion

On the basis of the composition studies it is revealed that cobalt(II) forms 1 : 2 complex with *m*-methylphenylazo-bis-acetoxime.

The stability constants were determined using the methods of Harvey and Manning² and Purohit³. The log *K* values obtained from both the methods agree well indicating the validity of the method. Further, precision studies considering ten values of absorbance gave precision studies of 0.063 ppm of cobalt(II). The above studies thus conclude that the reagent *m*-methylphenylazo-bis-acetoxime (*m*-MPABA) can be successfully applied for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II). Synthesis of reagent using simple reagents further advocates the utility of the reagent.

Interference studies : The effects of several interfering cations and anions on the absorbance of cobalt complex were studied at 10, 50 and 100 ppm levels of interfering ions. The anions and cations which did not interfere at 10 ppm level were screened at 50 ppm and 100 ppm. It was observed that NH₄⁺, Cu²⁺, Sn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, V⁴⁺, PO₄³⁻ ions interfered at 10 ppm level; Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Hg²⁺ interfered at 50 ppm level; Ba²⁺, SO₃²⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₂⁻, CH₃COO⁻, CO₃²⁻ interfered at 100 ppm level, whereas Na⁺,

K⁺, Br⁻, I⁻, Cl⁻ did not interfere even upto 100 ppm. Thus it can be concluded that using *m*-MPABA even in presence of upto 100 ppm of interfering ions, 11.79 ppm of cobalt(II) can be determined by this method.

Experimental

m-Methylphenylazo-bis-acetoxime was prepared by the reported method⁴. In the method, *p*-toluidine (11.3 g) was diazotized below 5°. Further, acetoxime was prepared by the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in aq. NaOH and acetone below 5°. The acetoxime was separated out. The diazotized product was coupled at 0° under mechanical stirring with a solution of acetoxime (12 g) in 10% NaOH (150 ml). Red coloured granular precipitate that separated out was filtered and washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The crude product was treated with activated charcoal, then crystallized twice from alcohol and obtained as reddish brown microcrystals, m.p. 82°.

A stock solution of cobalt (2 × 10⁻³ M) was prepared by dissolving cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (AnalaR) in double-distilled water and a few drops of conc. nitric acid were added to prevent hydrolysis. A stock solution of *m*-MPABA (2 × 10⁻³ M) was prepared in alcohol and dilute solutions were prepared using this stock solutions. Tris-buffer solution was prepared by dissolving tris-buffer [tris(hydroxymethyl)-aminomethane] (2.0 g) in minimum quantity of water and was then made up to 100 ml with ethanol.

A Systronics 108 UV-vis spectrophotometer and a Systronics 324 pH meter were used.

References

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